

METHODS AND WAYS OF TEACHING PRONUNCIATION

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Annotation: This article discusses pronunciation and its types. In addition, the article also talks about different methods of teaching pronunciation.

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"Pronunciation" refers to the way in which we make the sound of words. Styles of speech or pronunciation are those special forms of speech suited to the aim and the contents of the utterance, the circumstances of communication, the character of the audience. The style-differentiating characteristics mentioned good grounds for establishing intonational styles. There are five intonational styles singled out mainly according to the purpose of communication and to which we could refer all the main varieties of the texts. They are as follows:

1. Informational style.
2. Academic style (Scientific).
3. Publicistic style.
4. Declamatory style (Artistic).
5. Conversational style (Familiar).

But differentiation of intonation according to the purpose of communication is not enough; there are other factors that affect intonation in various situations. Besides any style is seldom realized in its pure form. Learning English pronunciations can be very challenging and time. And can you guess what more challenging - teaching it. The teaching process has got different objectives at each level. With this blog, you would be able to teach pronunciation by discussing different words at each level.

You can easily plan out your resources and activities which would help your students to improve their communication skills. One of the best ways would be to encourage them to converse in English. You need to introduce the complete idea that while they are doing their homework by reading aloud all the words. Sometimes students feel that they are pronouncing the words correctly. But only a listener can understand whether it is correct or not. But we have a solution here. Students can easily

record the words by actually saying it. Then you might have this empirical data to playback and listen to it carefully. You can encourage students to listen to what they are actually saying. Sometimes listening to the native speakers can also serve the purpose. With this technique, the students would have a more objective understanding of the words and proper pronunciation. If students are struggling to pronounce the entire word, then you can always make use of phonetic symbols which help to produce sound. In addition to that, you can make use of phonetics to introduce new vocabulary. You can read our blog (Englishbix phonetic sounds) to help students understand the sound produce by vowels. People nowadays learn the pronunciation of English in their own way which might not be the correct method. Hence its consequences will be that you end up making the wrong pronunciation of the words. In most language textbooks, you would look up for pronunciation and the sounds of various words are also explained through some audio.

This method might feel a bit convenient while you are learning some alphabets but it won't be very helpful in developing good pronunciation in learning words in English. In this way, all the letters will be in accordance with some phonological which would be from the other language and it will come with all of its peculiarities. For instance, there is a difference between how a Russian learns to pronounce 'T' and how it will be done by an American. Teaching pronunciation is an area of language teaching that many English teachers avoid. While there are many textbooks and instruction manuals available, there is comparatively little on learning pronunciation. Why? Is it because we don't need to teach pronunciation or because it cannot be taught? The importance of teaching pronunciation. Indeed, we should teach pronunciation because words can have different meanings depending on how you say them. For example, there is a big difference between a pear and a bear, two sounds that are not easy for Spaniards! A teacher's first goal for their students is to achieve basic communication. However, that can fail if their accent is so bad that no one can understand them. In addition, teaching pronunciation is necessary since it's embarrassing to ask someone to repeat themselves three times and still not understand them.

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